

SHOULD NURSES WORK LONG HOURS?

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993243>

Keywords

Healthcare providers, Wellbeing, Continuity of care, Errors

Article History

Received: 28 May, 2025

Accepted: 03 August, 2025

Published: 29 August, 2025

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Abstract

Working long hours is mandatory for many nurses in several hospitals in Pakistan. Longer shifts mean greater continuity of care, stronger professional bonds with patients, more days off, and a better work-life balance. But does it have a positive impact on nurses' well-being or have detrimental effects on their health?

INTRODUCTION

To ensure that patients receive continuous care, nurses operate in a variety of work shift schedules. According to certain studies, it is widely acknowledged that the accredited working hours last between eight to twelve hours a day. On the other hand, nurses occasionally need to work longer hours than planned. However, the topic is still debatable whether nurses should put in additional time at their shifts still exists. A study conducted by (Lin, Lin, Hsia, & Kuo, 2021) found that as patient demands fluctuate over time and staffing levels can change unexpectedly, actual shift lengths are frequently unpredictable. Because of this, nurses frequently work longer shifts than anticipated resulting in burnout and exhaustion ultimately posing a threat to the quality of patient care. Yet, if the working hours lengthen beyond normal, it won't just make the workers unhappy with their work, but also reduce their productivity, affect them bodily injury, and drive them to quit. This paper argues that should nurses work longer hours, which,

therefore, have an impact on employees' overall performance in addition to patient safety and the organization's status.

Background

A nurse will often need to work at least five days per week when working an 8-hour shift, but just three or four days per week if working a 12-hour shift. However, nurses no longer work the standard eight-hour shifts, and twelve-hour shifts are becoming more common and sometimes very alluring to nurses because it allows them to spend their day off with their families or pursue other interests. Research suggests that longer shifts allow nurses to form stronger professional bonds with their patients, which may help patients feel happier with the quality of care and treatment they receive. It aids nurses in remembering crucial information about their patients, particularly the care and treatment they offer to patients.

Furthermore, it allows patients to receive continuous care from the same nurse without switching nurses during shifts resulting in greater patient satisfaction scores and fewer chances for miscommunication and accidents. It also allows nurses to work flexible hours resulting in higher productivity and confidence among them, ultimately raising the standard of quality care. A nurse is better able to pick up on the complexities of a patient's health and side effects the more involved they are with them during their shift. This minute information frequently enables nurses to manage pain more skillfully and recognize abrupt patient health changes (Liu et al., 2022).

On the other hand, some people argue that employees become exhausted when they work longer than normal. Working multiple lengthy shifts in succession might interfere with sleep, and employees may find it challenging to stay alert throughout their shifts. As a result, there are more errors made, internal conflicts arise, and customer service suffers. The study conducted (Rajan, 2017) found that in comparison with a twelve long hour shift, an eight hour shift help nurses to reduce fatigue as the shorter working hours allow nurses to go home and sleep well. These downtimes help nurses to feel more rested and ready for their next shift. Another study done by (Hoedl, Bauer, & Eglseer, 2021) found that People who get care from nurses who work shorter shifts frequently express greater satisfaction with their care and time spent in medical facilities. Long working hours are linked to feelings of exhaustion, unhappiness, and depression among nurses which eventually results in individuals experiencing compromised care. Others believe that a higher number of workers who put in long hours were more likely to engage in unethical behavior, such as the abuse of organizational resources, and power, sexual harassment, and violating the organization's code of conduct.

Conclusion

Long work shifts have been shown to have several negative effects on nurses' overall health, as well as their job satisfaction and employment in comparison to positives. Hence, to implement the necessary measures to control working hours, hospital management must be aware of how

excessive working hours harm workers' social and physical well-being. To determine if longer shifts are useful or detrimental to their teams, hospital administrators must continuously monitor their staff and evaluate employee engagement levels. The key determinants of an employee's productivity are their health and job satisfaction, and working hours have a highly positive correlation with both. Leaders are urged to organize routine, manageable one-on-one meetings with nurses to review caseloads and determine areas in which support is required (Rhéaume & Mullen, 2018). Additionally, hospital management should focus on teaching staff members time management skills and how to balance work and family obligations because social and family relationships are crucial to one's health and happiness, which in turn affects how committed and motivated staff members are to their employer. Unfortunately, shift work is unavoidable in today's healthcare environment, but strategies could be implemented to mitigate the effects.

REFERENCES

- Hoedl, M., Bauer, S., & Eglseer, D. (2021). Influence of nursing staff working hours on stress levels during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional online survey. *HeilberufeScience*, 12(3-4), 92-98. doi:10.1007/s16024-021-00354-y
- Lin, R. T., Lin, Y. T., Hsia, Y. F., & Kuo, C. C. (2021). Long working hours and burnout in health care workers: Non-linear dose-response relationship and the effect mediated by sleeping hours-A cross-sectional study. *J Occup Health*, 63(1), e12228. doi:10.1002/1348-9585.12228
- Liu, S., Wang, C., Jiang, Y., Ren, H., Yu, T., Cun, W., & Yang, Z. (2022). Nurse scheduling in COVID-19-designated hospitals in China: A nationwide cross-sectional survey. *J Nurs Manag*, 30(8), 4024-4033. doi:10.1111/jonm.13832
- Rajan, D. (2017). Negative Impacts of Long Working Hours: A Comparative Study among Nurses. *MOJ Applied Bionics and Biomechanics*, 1. doi:10.15406/mojabb.2017.01.00010

Rhéaume, A., & Mullen, J. (2018). The impact of long work hours and shift work on cognitive errors in nurses. *J Nurs Manag*, 26(1), 26-32. doi:10.1111/jonm.12513

